

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA)

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Abstract :

In 2005, India's parliament passed the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA), which is the central government's response to the constitutionally manifested right to work and means to promote livelihood security in India's rural areas. To this end, the Act guarantees 100 days of annual employment at statutory minimum wage rates to any rural household whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work. The manual work needs to create sustainable assets that promote the economic and infrastructure development of villages. Implemented in three phases beginning in 2006, the Act extended to all of rural India in April 2008. NREGA is an innovative answer to the long-standing problem of providing social safety nets in rural areas. The overall objective of this paper is to bring focus on Issues and challenges of MGNREGA and to evaluate the performance since its enactment. Apart from academic perspective on the need, relevance and justification for the MGNREGA, it also seeks to establish a dialogue between academics and policy makers with those who are working at grass root level to monitor the functioning of the MGNREGA. Another objective of the paper is to bring together all these diverse experiences on a common platform to arrive at some common understandings on the problems faced in implementation of MGNREGA and also to learn from the successes in implementing MGNREGA.

Keywords : MGNREGA, Social development, Organization and Social security.

Introduction :

The Indian Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) was passed in September 2005 with the objective of addressing the statutory right to food security. The public Employment programme is Central Government scheme under the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD), with shared responsibility between national and state Government for its implementation. This programme was implemented in the year 2006 by then Dr. Manmohan government with an intention to provide minimum 100 days employment to farmers, labourers and other rural populace and was initiated in three phases : Phase - I (2006-2007) - the 200 most backward districts of the country; Phase - II (2007- 2008) - Extended to an Additional 130 Districts, and; Phase - III (2008 ONWARDS) - Extended to all Remaining Rural District.

MGNREGA is currently the largest funded Rural Development Programme in India with an annual budget of USD 8.44 billion in 2019-20, compared to an initial budget of 1.6 billion in 2006-07. MGNREGA is operational in 34 out of the 36 states and union territories, and 691 of the 712 districts, which includes 6,918 block and 2,62,432 Gram Panchayats, the lowest tier of the local Government system in India. It is the largest Public Employment Programme in the world employing 52 million people and creating 2.34 billion person-days of work in 2017-18. 128.5 million Rural households are registered in the scheme, and are eligible for work on demand (30.85% of India's rural population).

The Gist of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) :

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005 (or, NREGA no.42) was later renamed as the "Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act" (MGNREGA), is an Indian Labour Law and Social Security measure that aims to guarantee the "right of work". It aims to ensure livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. Starting from 200 districts on from 2, February 2006, the MGNREGA covered all the

districts of India from 1 April, 2008. The statute is hailed by the Government as “the largest and most ambitious social security and public works programme in the world”. In its world development report, 2014, the World Bank termed it a “stellar example of rural development”. The MGNREGA was initiated with the objective of enhancing livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year, to every house hold whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work”. Another aim of MGNREGA is to create durable assets (such as road, canals ponds, and wells). Employment is to be provided within 5 km of an applicant’s residence and minimum wage are to be paid. If work is not provided within 15 days of applying applicants are entitled to an unemployment allowance under MGNREGA is a legal entitlement.

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA)” is to be implemented mainly by Gram Panchayats (GPs). The involvement of contractors is banned. Labour intensive tasks like creating infrastructure for water harvesting, draught relief and flood control are preferred. Apart from providing economic security and creating rural asserts, NREGA can help in protecting the environment, empowering rural women, reducing rural-urban migration and fostering social equity among others. The law provides many safeguard to promote its effective management and implementation. The act explicitly mentions the principles and agencies for implementation, list of allowed works, financing pattern, monitoring and evaluation, and most importantly the detailed measures to ensure transparency and accountability.

Implementation :

The act is to be implemented by the state Government, with funding from the central Government. According to section 13, the principal authorities for planning and implementation of the scheme are the panchayats at the district, intermediate and village levels. The basic unit of implementation is the block. In each block, a “programme officer” will be charge. The programme officer is supposed to be and officer of rank on less than Block Development Officer (BDO), paid by the Central Government, and with the implementation of NREGA as his or her sole responsibility. The programme officer is accountable to the “intermediate panchayats” as well as to the district coordinator. Implementing agencies include any agency that is authorized by the central Government or the state Government to

undertake the implementation of any work” taken under NREGA (section 2(g)). The main implementing agencies are gram panchayats at least 50 percent of the works (in terms of share of the NREGA funds) have to be implemented through the gram panchayats(Section 16(5)). Other implementing agencies include Panchayat Samiti, the district panchayats and “line departments” such as the public works department, the forest department, the irrigation department, as so on. NREGA also allows, NGOs to act as implementing agencies. Even the works of implementing agencies other than the gram panchayat must be presented before the Gram Sabha and included in the annual shelf of works. The registration process involves an application to the gram panchayat and issue of job cards. The wage employment must be provided within 15 days of the date of application. The work entitlement of 100 days per house hold per year may be shared between different adult members of the same house hold.

The law also list permissible works: water conservation and after harvesting, draught proofing including afforestation, irrigation works, restoration of traditional water bodies, land development, flood control, rural connectivity and works notified by the Government. The act sets a minimum limit to the wages, to be paid with gender equality either on a time rate basis or on a piece rate basis. The state is required to evolve a set of norms for the measurement of works and schedule of rates. Unemployment allowance must be paid if the work is not provided within the statutory limit of 15 days. The law stipulates Gram Panchayats to have a single bank account for MGNREGA works which shall be subjected to public security. To promote transparency and accountability, the act mandates monthly squaring of accounts. To ensure public accountability through public vigilance, the NREGA designates ‘social audits’ as key to its implementation.

MGNREGA in A & N Islands : Issues and challenges :

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) was notified on September 7, 2005 and was implemented in April 2008 in Andaman and Nicobar Islands. ¹The objective of the Act is to enhance livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guarantee wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work.

Implementation structure :

1. Secretary (Rural Development / Panchayat) is designated as the State Rural Employment Guarantee Commissioner under MGNREGA at state level. He is also the Chairman of the Andaman and Nicobar state Employment Guarantee Fund Management Committee.
2. The directorate of Rural Development, Panchayat Raj Institutions and Urban Local Bodies is the Nodal Department of MGNREGA at State level.
3. Andaman and Nicobar State Employment Guarantee Council of MGNREGA has been created under the Chairmanship of Lieutenant Governor at State level to review the scheme.
4. At district level implementation agency is the Deputy Commissioner is designated as District Programme coordinator.
5. At Block level we have BDOs designated as Sr. Programme officer. The BDOs area assisted by the Programme officer and his supporting staff appointed on contract basis.
6. At Gram Panchayat level we have appointed Gram RozgarSewakson contract basis.

Salient features of the Act :

1. The job card is being issued within 15 days of registration to the rural households whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work.
2. A job card holder willing to work submits a written application for employment under MGNREGA to the Gram Panchayat / Gram RozgarSewak/ Programme Officer.
3. Employment is being given within 15 days of application for work, if it is not then daily unemployment allowance equal to $\frac{1}{4}$ of per day wage for first 30 days and $\frac{1}{2}$ of per day wage for remaining days has to be paid by the state. Till date no case of unemployment allowances has been registered by the districts to this Directorate.

4. Work is ordinarily being provided within 5km radius of the village. In case work is provided beyond 5km, extra wages of 10% are payable to meet additional transportations and livelong expenses.
5. At least one-third beneficiaries are women who have registered and requested work under the scheme.

Types of Activities taken up by District Administration under MGNREGA :

- a) Water conservation and water harvesting (ponds);
- b) Drought proofing including afforestation and tree plantation;
- c) Irrigation canals including micro and minor irrigation water;
- d) Provision of irrigation facility, dug out farm pond, horticulture, plantation and farm bundling ;
- e) Renovation of traditional water bodies including desalting of tanks;
- f) Land development;
- g) Flood control and protection works including drainage in water logged;
- h) Rural connectivity to provide all weather access;
- i) Livestock related works, such as poultry shelter.

The table - 1 shows that category wise household / workers of financial year 2021-2022 in Andaman & Nicobar Islands. In Nicobar District total 5930 Workers applied for job cards out of which 5812 job cards were issued. Total numbers of registered workers is 9600 out of which SC's - 4, ST's - 6442, others - 3154 and women - 4117. Number of active job cards are 617, Total number of active workers is 895 in which SCs - 0, STs - 809, others - 86 and women is 414. In North and Middle Andaman District, total 18056 Workers applied for job cards out of which 17327 job cards were issued. Total number of registered workers is 28744 in which SCs - 0, STs - 0, others - 28744 and women - 12488. Number of active job cards are 7400 and total active workers is 9825 including SC's, ST's, others and Women is 5070. In South Andaman District total 9548 Workers applied for job cards out of which 9479 job cards were issued. Total registered workers are 12357 including SC's, ST's, others and Women is 6476. Number of active job cards are 4056 and total active workers is 4581 including SC's, ST's, others and Women is 2674.

Table - 1
Category Wise Household/ Workers (2021-2022)
State : Andaman and Nicobar Islands

S. No.	Districts	No. of job cards		Registered Workers					No. of Active job Cards*	Active worker*				
		Applied for	Issued	SCs	STs	Others	Total Workers	Women		SCs	STs	Others	Total Workers	Women
1	2 ▲	3 ↑↓	4 ↑↓	5 ↑↓	6 ↑↓	7 ↑↓	8 ↑↓	9 ↑↓	10 ↑↓	11 ↑↓	12 ↑↓	13 ↑↓	14 ↑↓	15 ↑↓
	Total	33534	32618	4	6442	44255	50701	23081	12073	0	809	14492	15301	8158
1	Nicobar	5930	5812	4	6442	3154	9600	4117	617	0	809	86	895	414
2	North and Middle Andaman	18056	17327	0	0	28744	28744	12488	7400	0	0	9825	9825	5070
3	South Andaman	9548	9479	0	0	12357	12357	6476	4056	0	0	4581	4581	2674
	Total	33534	32618	4	6442	44255	50701	23081	12073	0	809	14492	15301	8158

Source : Directorate of Rural Development (RD), Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) and Urban Local Bodies(ULBs), Andaman and Nicobar Administration, Port Blair.

The table - 2 shows that Age wise person employed in financial year 2021-2022, in Andaman & Nicobar Islands. There are three Districts - Nicobar, North and Middle Andaman and South Andaman District. In the given age group of 18-30, Total 2.75% people registered in which employed person are 5%. In the given age group of 31-40, Total 33.81% people registered in which employed person are 32.39%. In the given age group of 41-50, Total 29.89% people registered in which employed person are 35.51%. In the given age group of 51-60, Total 17.46% people registered in which employed person are 17.84%. In the given age group of 61-80, Total 14.53% people registered in which employed person are 8.94%. In the given age group greater than 80, Total 1.56% people registered in which employed person are 0.32%.

Table - 2

Age-wise Persons Employed in Financial Year - 2021-2022
State : Andaman and Nicobar Islands

⊙ Percentage ○ In Numbers

		Age wise Registered and Employed Persons											
S. No.		18-30		31-40		41-50		51-60		61-80		Greater than 80	
		Registered person since beginning	Employed persons	Registered person since beginning	Employed persons	Registered person since beginning	Employed persons	Registered person since beginning	Employed persons	Registered person since beginning	Employed persons	Registered person since beginning	Employed persons
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	Nicobars	3.15	NaN	38.64	NaN	29.17	NaN	17.51	NaN	11.1	NaN	0.43	NaN
2	North and Middle Andaman	2.89	4.55	27.49	33.59	22.73	35.97	13	17.56	11.45	8.01	1.2	0.32
3	South Andaman	0.59	1.42	12.03	5.92	12.24	7.17	7.25	4.01	6.1	2.63	0.77	0.07
	Total	2.75	5	33.81	32.39	29.89	35.51	17.46	17.84	14.53	8.94	1.56	0.32

Achievements of MGNREGA made in A & N Islands :

The MGNREGA scheme in the UT of A & N Islands has offered employment during the lockdown to the unemployed beneficiaries who were in need of a way of employment for their livelihood. MGNREGA was a fallback option to those who need it; MGNREGA played the role of sole source of income for rural households. It is often the sole income source for many rural households, pandemic or not.

Amidst the lockdown, MGNREGA has taken up works with the prime motive to provide employment to the rural population for their livelihood and has successfully generated around 55,673 persondays and around 2660 Households are provided employment during the year 2021-22. In the year 2020-21, the MGNREGA scheme had generated around 2.90 lakhs of persondays.

The active workers in the UT of A & N Islands are around 15,356. The MGNREGA offers employment to all the unemployed workers willing to perform manual works from the age of 18 years. Around 54% of the workers engaged in the scheme are women and around 6% of the workers belong to scheduled caste. The approved labour budget for the F.Y, is 2.50 lakhs but till date only 0.55673 lakhs persondays are achieved.

Conclusion :

To conclude, MGNREGA has not only created employment opportunities in rural areas but also created durable assets which in turn further improved resource base for livelihoods of rural people. Besides, MGNREGA has also strengthened rural local Governments as there are principal authorities to implement the act. However, there are some deficiencies in the implementation of the act as revealed by various studies, evaluations and audit reports. Adequate care has also been taken to rectify these deficiencies from time to time. The recent initiatives taken in this regard will further improve the implementation of the act in the rural areas of the country. It is expected that there would be better implementation of the act in the days ahead. MGNREGA has been one of the most celebrated and one of the most successful programmes of the Indian Government in its 60 years history. Some of the chief players in conceiving this programme have been the bureaucracy, the planning commission and the Government in general. It is not only a programme which has taken the effort of the best of bureaucrats and economics, but also a result of the various attempts made over a number of years, in the name of planning and other policy makings. Apart from the basic outline of MGNREGA there have been various other implications to MGNREGA such as the general price rise in the daily wages of the labourers and the general increase in the number of people needed to implement it causing a higher supply of jobs than envisaged by the programme.

The other major impact of MGNREGA has been on the political parties. It has managed to trigger the urge in the political parties to serve the poor in the rural areas, causing a sort parties who have developmental initiatives and have campaigns of their own. But MGNREGA caused almost every political party to think about it as a tool for popularity among the poor. For once in the history of political India, any party has decided to implement a programme introduced by someone else and also has done that to improve its own image.

The World Bank had its own takes on MGNREGA, and as is always the case with the World Bank, it came up with a completely skewed observation about it. Its statements that MGNREGA was clogging urbanization and was also making land owning farmers lives uncomfortable were criticized the most in the Indian media. The world banks basic assumptions that it is the producer who is more important than the consumer and the assumption the urbanization was desirable over rural development were seen as the biggest flaws in its arguments. And once again proved its skewedness towards the capitalist countries from which it is funded. Whether the World Bank likes it or not, MGNREGA remains one of the most well drafted policies by the Indian government, something that is truly thinking about the poor.

References :

1. Government of India (2012) : “The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005”, Ministry of Rural Development, New Delhi.
2. Mathur L. (2007) : “Employment Guarantee: Progress so far”. Economic and Political Weekly, December 2007.
3. R.V. R. Murthy : Andaman and Nicobar Islands: Development and Decentralization, Mittal Publication, New Delhi, 2005.
4. <http://nrega.nic.in>
5. Andaman and Nicobar Administration, Andaman and Nicobar Island at Directorate of Rural Development (RD), Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) Administration, Port Blair, 2021.

6. Sabita Kumari : “Rural Employment Schemes in India”, October 2014.
7. Dr. Joseph Abraham : “MGNREGA - Need for Reforms to create productive Rural Employment”, October 2014.
8. Dr. Mahi Pal : “Impact of MGNREGA on Employment Generation and Capital Formation”, October 2014.